

DETERMINANTS OF SURVIVAL OF COASTAL VILLAGE COMMUNITIES (STUDY OF THE CANGGU VILLAGE COMMUNITY, NORTH KUTA - BALI)

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Abstract

In general, coastal areas are relatively far from the center of government, with minimal facilities and infrastructure compared to inland (urban) areas. Likewise, the government's attention to coastal village communities is somewhat lacking, so the quality of human resources in coastal villages is underdeveloped. The touch of technology is also late compared to city communities, but the culture and social relations between village communities are still influential. In connection with these conditions, this research aims to analyze the influence of the role of government, human resources, culture, technology, and social capital on community survival. This research was conducted in the coastal communities of Canggu Village, North Kuta-Bali, whose population is 1,200 heads of families. The research sample was determined using the Slovin formula at a precision level of %, so the total research sample was 300 heads of families. The sampling technique was carried out simply at random. Next, data was collected by conducting direct interviews based on a prepared questionnaire. The data collected was then tested for validity and reliability to ensure the research data was valid and reliable. Data analysis was carried out with the SmartPLS 3.2.9 application program. The analysis results show that the role of government, culture, and technology is significantly positive in the social capital of coastal village communities. At the same time, the influence of human resources is not significant. The research results also found that human resources, the role of government, culture, and social capital significantly influence the survival of coastal village communities. Social capital can mediate the relationship between the role of government, culture, and technology in the survival of coastal village communities. The results of this research mean that the role of government, culture, and technology will have a better influence on the survival of coastal communities if the community's social capital is also improved.

Keywords: Human Resources, Government, Local Culture, Technology, Social Capital, Life Resilience, Coastal Communities.

INTRODUCTION

The Covid 19 pandemic, which has spread since mid-February 2020, has caused many people in the world to lose their livelihoods to support their survival, including in Indonesia in general and Bali in particular. Moreover, Bali, a tourist destination visited by many tourists from various countries, was isolated then, and no tourists came to Bali like before Covid. Since then, Bali has been very quiet from tourist visits, with most Balinese people relying heavily on tourism activities.

Since then, Bali's economy has declined sharply, and many employees working in the tourism sector have reduced their working hours; some have even been laid off and laid off to minimize losses (Honoatubun in Sayuti and Hidayati, 2020). Many employees had their working hours reduced, and they were laid off and laid off, causing them to lose their livelihoods and income. This is felt by people involved in the tourism sector, especially those in tourism areas such as the Canggu Village Community, North Kuta.

Canggu Village is one of the villages that are tourist destinations in Bali. This village is located on the coast of Kuta Beach, also known as a global village, and is inhabited mainly by tourists. Before becoming a tourist destination, the livelihoods of most of the people of Canggu Village were farmers, fishermen, and laborers.

However, after developing into a tourist destination, where much land was used as a buffer for tourism, many Canggu Village residents changed their profession to become tourism practitioners. The transition from farmer to tourism actor is seen as an upward vertical transition (transformation), namely a movement to a better social status (Sri Muhamad, 2019). However, since the Covid 19 outbreak, Canggu Village has been empty of tourists, so people have lost their livelihood from the tourism sector.

Many Canggu Village residents have changed professions to support their families, including becoming farmers, fishermen, builders, and so on. The transition or transformation from tourism to agriculture is seen as a downward vertical transformation (Prabawati, 2009). Most of the people of Canggu Village did this to survive the uncertainty during the pandemic.

Due to the self-awareness of the people of Canggu Village and their commitment to survive at that time, as well as hard work, the people of Canggu Village can still survive well without being entirely dependent on the tourism sector. All of this could be due to human resource capabilities, culture, technological developments, and the social capital of the people of Canggu Village. This research focuses on the extent to which these factors can influence the survival of the people of Canggu Village.

THEORETICAL, EMPIRICAL, AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Community Survival

According to Walker et al. (2004), survival is defined as the capacity of a system to absorb and reorganize when experiencing change to maintain the same function, structure, and feedback. According to Van Holk (2008), resilience describes a process where people manage efforts to overcome life's difficulties, create and maintain a meaningful life, and contribute to the people around them.

Meanwhile, according to Simmie and Martin (2010), resilience is defined as a system's ability to rebound to restore itself to an elastically balanced shape and position after a disturbance occurs. Building family resilience is defined as the family's material ability to live independently and develop the resources they have (Yohana et al. (2016:79).

Community resilience can also be interpreted as the ability of individuals, groups, or communities to overcome external pressures and disturbances when undergoing social change, politics and the environment (Adger, 2000). Resilience is the ability to bounce back or overcome dangerous events and embedded vulnerabilities (Manyena, 2006). Resilience in the form of maintaining the ability to face stress means overcoming problems despite experiencing challenging circumstances. (Siahaan, 2012).

The concept of the survival approach refers to the sustainable livelihood approach theory (from now on referred to as SLA), where in this theory, it is stated that in order to survive in life, people must have the ability to manage at least 5 main assets (the Pentagon assets), namely human capital, natural capital, social capital, physical capital, and financial capital.

Diagrammatically, the relationship between these five factors is depicted as follows.

Figure 1: Asset Pentagonal Diagram

Source: Translated from DFID, “Sustainable Livelihoods Guidance Sheets”, 1999

Human capital is the primary and most important capital in the form of skills, experience, knowledge, and creativity, which can be used to manage other capital, such as natural capital, social capital, physical capital, and financial capital. Next is natural capital, namely resources owned by nature such as land, water, forests and grasslands, and minerals. If this natural capital is managed well, together with human capital, financial capital, and other capital, it will be able to maintain the sustainability of economic life. The following capital is physical: houses, tools and machines, food or livestock stocks, jewelry, and agricultural equipment, which can be used by human capital and other capital to maintain and increase survival. Next is financial capital, namely money in savings, loans, or credit accounts. This capital also has a significant role in maintaining human survival. Finally, social capital refers to the quality of relationships between people, for example, whether someone can rely on support from one family or help from neighbors (mutual). All of these capitals play a considerable role in maintaining human survival.

Apart from these capitals, the role of government and local culture also has a role that should be appreciated for the survival of a community. The government's role is shown in the form of physical and non-physical development, which directly or indirectly impacts the survival and welfare of the community. Meanwhile, the role of local culture is shown in the form of caring between community members, high levels of social interaction, and a culture of mutual assistance (helping) fellow community members.

Social Capital

Social capital is interpreted as a description of the internal ties that color the collective structure and provide cohesiveness and mutual benefits from the social dynamic processes in community life (Adler and Kwon (2002). Supriono (2008) states that social capital is the relationships created and norms that shape the quality and quantity of social relations in society in a broad spectrum, namely as the social glue that maintains the unity of members of society. Cohen and Prusak L. (2001) state that social capital is the basis of every relationship. It is bound by trust, mutual understanding, and shared values that bind group members to enable joint action to be carried out efficiently and effectively. In line with Cohen and Prusak L. (2021),

Hasbullah (2006) explains social capital as everything related to cooperation within a society or nation to achieve a better capacity for life, supported by values and norms, which are the main elements such as trust (mutual trust).

Social capital has aspects of trust, cooperation, work networks, and so on). In rural social life, trust can be seen as a matter of personality or intrapersonal, extrapersonal, and intersubjective aspects (Budi and Ardian, 2012). These aspects greatly influence community survival.

Several research results have proven that social capital in all its aspects can influence community survival, such as the results of research conducted by Aldrich & Meyer (2015), Aldrich (2017), Musavengane & Kloppers (2020), Tippens (2020), Safii & Rahayu (2021); Carmen et al. (2022); Maulana & Wardah (2023); Prayitno et al. (2023). Based on these arguments, the following research hypothesis can be built.

Hypothesis-1: Social Capital has a significant positive effect on community survival

Social capital is also a factor that can be influenced by several other factors, such as human resource capabilities, the role of government, the role of local culture, and technological developments.

Human Resources

Human resources (in this case, skills, expertise, experience, creativity, innovation, etc.) are energy (power) that can be used to create economic and business value (McGregor et al., 2004; Karami et al., 2006). According to Pasolong (2013:5), Quality human resources are highly knowledgeable, skilled, and morally competent workers. Meanwhile, according to Ndraha (2012: 12), quality human resources are human resources capable of creating not only comparative value but also competitive, generative, and innovative value by using the highest energy, such as intelligence, creativity, and imagination, no longer merely the eye uses gross energy such as raw materials, land, water, muscle energy, and so on. The higher the quality of human resources, the higher their social abilities and ability to manage other resources to maintain their lives. Human resource capital in this research includes the quantity, quality, and skills of human resources at the research site.

The research results that prove the existence of a relationship between human capital and social capital are Denny (2023). Meanwhile, research results that found a relationship between human capital and community survival include Hakim, A. R. (2023). Based on this argument, the following research hypothesis can be built.

Hypothesis-2: Human resources have a significant positive effect on social capital

Hypothesis-3: Human resources have a significant positive effect on community survival

Role of Government

The government has a massive role in maintaining the resilience of its people through various physical and non-physical developments (Siagian, 2000). In physical terms, the government can build various facilities and infrastructure to improve the community's economy, such as roads, bridges, markets, etc. The role of non-physical government is that the government can play the role of stabilizer, innovator, modernizer, and pioneer in development in all fields. In this research, the role of government is shown through indicators: village government assistance, synergy

between traditional government and government agencies, and other government programs.

The government has a massive role in increasing society's social capital. This is evident from several research studies that found that the role of government is significant in society's social capital, including the results of research conducted by Warner (2001) and Ponzetto & Troiano (2018). Apart from that, several research results also prove that the government's role significantly impacts community survival. The results of these studies include Platts & Robinson (2016), Fransen et al. (2022), and O'Grady & Shaw (2023). Based on the results of this research, the following research hypothesis can be built.

Hypothesis-4: The role of government has a significant positive effect on social capital

Hypothesis-5: The role of government has a significant positive effect on community survival

Local Culture

Culture is a complex unit that includes science, belief, art, morals, law, custom, and many other abilities and habits humans acquire as members of society. The local culture of an area dramatically influences the human resource capital in that place. A strict local culture that strictly regulates and limits most of the community's behavior will weaken the community's social capital. On the other hand, if a developing local culture provides extensive freedom or opportunities for the community to increase their social capital, it will increase their social capital. Apart from that, local culture also closely relates to community life's resilience. Several research results have found a relationship between local culture and social capital, including Murzyn-Kupisz & Działek (2013). Meanwhile, research results that found a relationship between local culture and community survival include Surtiari et al. (2017) and Skevington & WHOQOL SRPB Group (2020). Based on the arguments as presented, the following research hypothesis can be built.

Hypothesis-6: Culture has a significant positive effect on social capital

Hypothesis-7: Culture has a significant positive effect on people's survival

Technology

Technology can be defined as entities, objects, and intangibles that are created in an integrated manner through actions and thoughts to achieve value. In this usage, technology refers to tools and machines that can be used to solve real-world problems. It is a wide-ranging term, and it can also include simple tools, such as crowbars or wooden spoons, or complex machines, such as space stations or particle accelerators. Tools and machines do not have to be tangible objects; virtual technologies, such as software and business methods, are also included in this definition of technology (Macek et al. 2007). In this case, technology refers to tools and machines that can be used to solve problems in the real world. Technology is a wide-ranging term, and it can also include simple tools, such as a crowbar or wooden spoon, or complex machines, such as a space station or particle accelerator. Tools and machines do not have to be tangible objects; virtual technologies, such as software and business methods, are also included in the definition of this technology (Science and Engineering Indicators. 2002). Technology and information are related to social capital and community survival. The higher the ability to master technology, the higher the

social capital and the ability to survive. Several research results have proven a relationship between technological and social capital and community survival. The research found the influence of technological capital on social capital, as in the research results of Sherif et al. (2026). Meanwhile, the results of research that found the influence of the role of technology on survival, namely Hills et al. (2018); Nasution, A. P., & Pristiyono, P. (2019); Al-Emran & Griffy-Brown (2023). Based on this explanation, the following research hypothesis can be built.

Hypothesis-8. Technology has a significant positive effect on social capital

Hypothesis-9. Technology has a significant positive effect on people's survival

As has been explained logically, empirically, and theoretically, community survival can be directly influenced by social capital, human capital, the role of government, local culture, and technology. Likewise, community survival can be influenced indirectly by human capital, the role of government, local culture, and technology through social capital. Based on these arguments, a research hypothesis can be built as follows.

Hypothesis-10: Social capital plays a mediating role in the relationship between human resources and survival

Hypothesis-11: Social capital plays a mediating role in the relationship between the role of government and survival

Hypothesis-12: Social capital plays a mediating role in the relationship between cultural roles and survival

Hypothesis-13: Social capital plays a mediating role in the relationship between the role of technology and survival

RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL

Based on the background description, theoretical and empirical studies, community survival can be directly influenced by human capital, the role of government, local culture, technology and social capital. In the next section, human capital, the role of government, local culture and technology have an indirect influence on community survival through social capital. Based on the results of this study, the following research conceptual framework can be built.

Figure 1: Research Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This research was designed with a correlative quantitative approach, namely research that correlates the independent variables (in this case, human resource capital, and the role of government, local culture, and technology) with the mediating dependent variable (social capital) and the dependent variable (community survival).

The research was conducted in Canggu Village, North Kuta District, Badung Regency, Bali. This location was chosen because it is an area developing to become the regional economic center of Badung Regency; it is also one of the world's best surfing spots and is unique as a "global village."

The population is the people of Canggu Village, numbering 1,200 heads of families. Meanwhile, the number of research samples was determined based on the Slovin formula with an error rate of 5%. Based on the Slovin formula calculation results, a sample size of 300 heads of families was obtained. The research sample was determined randomly.

Research data was collected using a questionnaire that had been prepared and tested for validity and reliability. The data that has been collected is then analyzed using the SPSS and SmartPLS application programs.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Validity, Reliability, and Fit Model

Testing the validity of research data is based on convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is measured based on the outer loading value of each indicator as in the following table. Data can be declared convergently valid if the original sample value of each indicator is greater than 0.50.

Table 1: Evaluation of Data Validity through Convergent Validity Values

No.	Variable Relationships	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Description
1	HR.1 <- HR	0.945	104.134	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
2	HR.2 <- HR	0.964	205.347	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
3	HR.3 <- HR	0.880	60.013	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
4	GR.1 <- GR	0.820	43.742	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
5	GR.2 <- GR	0.842	42.938	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
6	GR.3 <- GR	0.888	61.620	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
7	C.1 <- C	0.897	65.759	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
8	C.2 <- C	0.891	55.584	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
9	C.3 <- C	0.741	18.582	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
10	C.4 <- C	0.841	37.949	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
11	T.1 <- T	0.909	98.086	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid

12	T.2 <- T	0,882	52.698	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
13	SL.1 <- SL	0.764	29.717	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
14	SL.2 <- SL	0.752	31.878	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
15	SL.3 <- SL	0.775	28.445	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
16	SL.4 <- SL	0.745	29.741	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
17	SL.5 <- SL	0.669	17.115	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
18	SL.6 <- SL	0.754	24.756	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
19	SL.7 <- SL	0.783	36.606	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
20	SL.8 <- SL	0.785	35.921	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
21	SL.9 <- SL	0.598	13.062	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
22	SC.1 <- SC	0.792	24.313	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
23	SC.2 <- SC	0.912	67.450	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid
24	SC.3 <- SC	0.795	28.149	0.000	t-statistic >1.96 or p-value <0.05 → valid

Source: Processed data, 2023

Based on Table 1, it appears that the original sample value for each indicator for each variable meets the valid requirements, namely greater than 0.50, so that all data can be declared valid.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity

Variable	AVE	√AVE	HR	GR	C	T	SL	SC
HR	0.866	0.930	0.930					
GR	0.723	0.850	0.551	0.850				
C	0.714	0.845	0.342	0.492	0.845			
T	0.753	0.895	0.387	0.623	0.424	0.895		
SL	0.895	0.739	0.662	0.711	0.554	0.636	0.739	
SC	0.780	0.835	0.478	0.654	0.562	0.656	0.711	0.835

Source: Processed data, 2023

Validity testing via discriminant validity is shown in Table 2 below. The condition for the validity of a variable is expressed by the root value of AVE being greater than the correlation value between other variables.

Pay attention to Table 2, where the AVE root value ranges from 0.714 - 0.930, while the highest correlation value between other variables is 0.711. Thus, discriminately all research variables are declared valid.

Testing the reliability of research data is shown through the composite reliability and Cronbach Alpha values, shown in Table 3 below. Research variables can be declared reliable if the composite reliability value or Cronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.70.

Table 3: Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
HR	0.922	0.951	Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha >0,70 → Reliable
GR	0.808	0.887	Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha >0.70 → Reliable
C	0.865	0.908	Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha >0.70 → Reliable
T	0.753	0.890	Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha >0,70 → Reliable
SL	0.895	0.915	Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha >0.70 → Reliable
SC	0.780	0.873	Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha >0,70 → Reliable

Source: Processed data, 2023

Paying attention to the results of data analysis as in table 3, where the composite reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values show greater than 0.70, then all variables can be declared reliable.

Next, testing the level of accuracy of the research model was carried out. The accuracy of the research model is evaluated through R Square (R²) and Q Square Predictive Relevance (Q²).

The accuracy of the research model seen from R² is shown in Table 4, where human capital, the role of government, local culture and technology show a moderate influence, namely 0.589 (58.9%) on social capital. Meanwhile, the influence of human capital, the role of government, local culture, technology and social capital on community survival is strong, namely 0.765 (76.5%).

Table 4: R Square

Endogen Construct	R Square	Information
SC	0.589	Moderate
SL	0.765	Kuat

Source: Processed data, 2023

The accuracy of the research model via Q Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) is calculated using the following formulation

$$Q^2 = 1 - \{(1-R^2_1) (1-R^2_2)\}$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - \{(1-0.589) (1-0.765)\}$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - 0.096$$

$$Q^2 = 0.904$$

The results of the Q Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) calculation show a value of 0.904. This result shows that the research model has a high level of accuracy (90.4%).

Because the results of research data testing have shown to be valid, reliable and accurate, further analysis can be continued.

Hypothesis Result

Research hypothesis testing is based on Figure 2 and Table 5. Based on Figure 2 and Table 5, it can be described as follows.

Figure 2: SmartPLS Analysis Results

Table 5: Direct and Indirect Effects

No.	Hubungan Variabel	Path Coef	T Statistics	P Values	Description
1	SC -> SL	0.277	3.562	0.000	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H1-Accepted
2	HR -> SC	0.122	1.896	0.059	t-statistic <1.96/p-value>0.05 → no-signifikan → H2-Rejected
3	HR -> SL	0.272	6.030	0.000	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H3-Accepted
4	GR -> SC	0.246	2.875	0.004	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H4-Accepted
5	GR -> SL	0.337	5.316	0.000	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H5-Accepted
6	C -> SC	0.251	3.938	0.000	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H6-Accepted
7	C -> SL	0.098	2.475	0.014	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H7-Accepted
8	T -> SC	0.349	5.119	0.000	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H8-Accepted
9	T -> SL	0.098	1.630	0.104	t-statistic <1.96/p-value>0.05 → no-signifikan → H9-Rejected
10	HR ->SC->SL	0.034	1.624	0.105	t-statistic <1.96/p-value>0.05 → no-signifikan → H10-Rejected
11	GR ->SC ->SL	0.068	2.188	0.029	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H11-Accepted
12	C ->SC->SL	0.069	2.685	0.007	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H12-Accepted
13	T ->SC->SL	0.097	3.000	0.003	t-statistic >1.96/p-value<0.05 → Signifikan → H13-Accepted

Source: Processed data, 2023

Paying attention to Figure 2 and Table 5, it can be stated that SC (social capital), human resources, the role of government, and local culture have a positive influence on the survival of coastal communities in Canggu Village. Meanwhile, technology has no significant impact on the survival of the coastal communities of Canggu village.

On the other hand, human resources, the role of government, local culture and technology have a significant positive influence on social capital, while human resources have no significant influence on social capital.

Social capital is able to play a mediating role in the relationship between the role of government, local culture and technology on the survival of the coastal communities of Canggu Village, but is unable to mediate the relationship between human resources and the resilience of the coastal communities of Canggu Village.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the results and analysis of research data as stated above, social capital significantly influences the survival of coastal communities in Canggu Village. The social capital developing in the coastal communities of Canggu Village can support the survival of the Canggu village community.

Social capital can also mediate the relationship between the role of government, local culture, and technology on community survival. This means that the social capital that develops in the coastal communities of Canggu Village can bridge the role of government, culture, and technology with the survival of the Canggu village community.

However, human capital has no real influence on social capital, so in this case, social capital does not play a mediating role in the relationship between human resources and community survival. On the other hand, technology also has no significant impact on the survival of the people of Canggu Village. To further improve community resilience, especially communities in coastal areas, it is necessary to strengthen social capital, human resource competence, and local cultural consistency.

LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This research was specifically carried out in the coastal village community of Canggu Village, which is a tourist destination. The results of this research certainly cannot be generalized to other coastal villages, so research needs to be carried out for coastal village communities which are not tourist destinations. This can be done to obtain findings that may be different compared to coastal villages which are not tourist destination villages.

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